

1 **FingerPro: An R package for tracking the provenance of sediment**

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8

9 **ABSTRACT**

10 Soil loss by erosion processes is one of the largest challenges for food production and
11 reservoir siltation around the world. Information on sediment, nutrients and pollutants is
12 required for designing effective control strategies. The estimation of sediment sources is
13 difficult to get using conventional techniques, but sediment fingerprinting is a potentially
14 valuable tool. This procedure intends to develop methods that enable to identify the
15 apportionment of sediment sources from sediment mixtures.

16 We developed a new tool to quantify the provenance of sediments in an agroforest
17 catchment. For the first time, the procedure for the selection of the best combination of
18 tracers was included in the tool package. An unmixing model algorithm is applied to the
19 sediment samples to estimate the contribution of each possible source. The operations are
20 compiled in an R package named **FingerPro**, which unmixes sediment samples after
21 selecting the optimum set of tracers. An example from a well-studied Mediterranean
22 catchment is included in the package to test the model. The sediment source
23 apportionments are compared with previous results of soil redistributions where ¹³⁷Cs
24 derived rates validate the unmixing results, highlighting the potential of sediment
25 fingerprinting for quantifying the main sediment provenance. Fingerprinting techniques

26 will allow us to better comprehend sediment transport to water ecosystems and reservoirs
27 and its detrimental effect on the quality of the water and aquatic habitats.

28 The **FingerPro** package provides further understanding of the unmixing procedure
29 through the use of graphical and statistical tools, offering a broader and easier application
30 of the technique.

31 **KEYWORDS:** **FingerPro**, unmixing model, sediment source fingerprinting, source
32 variability, R package

33

34 **1. INTRODUCTION**

35 Reliable information on sediment loads transported by a river or stream is crucial to
36 evaluate the severity of reservoir siltation and river pollution. However, determining
37 sediment provenance or sediment budgets in catchments using conventional monitoring
38 techniques is often challenging. However, in most situations, it can be provided by
39 applying tracing techniques. Fingerprinting techniques can be used to recognise sediment
40 sources and to determine their relative contribution, thereby allowing the identification
41 of areas or land uses prone to erosion processes ([Schuller et al. 2013](#)). Soil erosion and
42 subsequent sediment transport are related to the loss of nutrients and their distribution in
43 the catchment ([Lizaga et al. 2019](#)). To assess this issue, several software and indices have
44 been developed to quantify the effects of different erosion mechanisms, such as
45 connectivity ([Shore et al. 2013](#)), runoff ([dos Santos et al. 2017](#)), sheet and rill ([Molnár
46 and Julien, 1998](#)), wind erosion ([Schmidt et al.. 2017](#)) and the subsequent effects on water
47 quality ([Panagopoulos et al. 2011](#); [Foucher et al. 2020](#)). However, sediment source
48 fingerprinting has been developed in recent decades for catchment sediment and pollutant
49 investigation as the most powerful tool to assess this problem. The procedure identifies

50 sediment provenance and estimates the relative contribution of each potential source,
51 using the selected tracer properties.

52 The first fingerprinting approach dates back to the seventies, based on mineralogical
53 and grain size characterisation (Klages and Hsieh, 1975). The earliest fingerprinting
54 studies were fundamentally qualitative in their result, but the introduction of quantitative
55 mixing models was a methodological advance that enabled researchers to obtain
56 quantitative results of the relative contribution from different sediment sources (Collins
57 et al. 1997). Since these early works, sediment source fingerprinting applications have
58 been greatly expanding with the development of new techniques (Owens et al. 2016).

59 The traditional approach for applying source-tracing methods is to define the relevant
60 tracer properties that provide a particular signature between all source samples and
61 unequivocally discriminate the different sources (Collins and Walling, 2002). Due to the
62 inherent complexity of catchment characteristics, with large variations in climate,
63 geology, land use, vegetation, soil, and management practices, commonly, no unique
64 tracer can discriminate between multiple sediment sources. Consequently, different tracer
65 properties need to be analysed, such as radionuclides (Wallbrink et al. 1998; Evrard et al.,
66 2020; Navas et al., 2020), geochemistry (Martínez-Carreras et al. 2010; Smith and Blake,
67 2014; Gaspar et al., 2019a), ultraviolet-visible spectra derived tracers (Ramon et al.,
68 2020), CSSI (Reiffarth et al. 2019) and eDNA (Evrard et al. 2019).

69 The fundamental theory that supports this technique is that the tracer properties of the
70 sediment mixtures are directly comparable to the sediment of the sources. A common
71 procedure, the so-called “range test”, checks if sediment tracers are conservative
72 excluding the tracers of the mixture/s outside the minimum and maximum values in the
73 potential sediment sources. This procedure prevents the inclusion in the optimum tracers
74 of the fingerprint properties exhibiting non-conservative behaviour. However, the

75 exclusion of a great number of fingerprint properties likely suggests that not all sources
76 have been correctly identified or characterised. Thus, the methodology for tracer selection
77 is an open question that is being discussed at present by several authors since different
78 tracer selection methods could lead models to different results (Pulley et al. 2015; Lizaga
79 et al. 2020). Following this assumption, the two-stage statistical procedure previously
80 proposed by Collins and Walling, (2002), is commonly used to assess this
81 conservativeness. Thus, the Kruskal Wallis H test (KW) and discriminant function
82 analysis (DFA) test the ability of individual tracers to discern between sediment sources
83 and select the best combination of tracers. This procedure was used to select the smallest
84 combination of tracers that provided the maximum discrimination of the identified source
85 categories and it is implemented by several authors as a common procedure when using
86 frequentist (Palazón et al. 2015; Lin et al. 2015; Gholami et al., 2020) and Bayesian
87 (Koiter et al. 2013; Barthod et al. 2015) unmixing models. Subsequently, the relative
88 contribution of each identified source is estimated using a linear multivariate unmixing
89 model.

90 Due to the growing use of fingerprinting methods, other unmixing models, such as
91 SIFT (Pulley and Collins, 2018), MixSIR (Moore and Semmens, 2008) and IsoSource
92 (Phillips and Gregg, 2003), appeared in the last years for pollution and ecological
93 purposes. However, due to operational complexity and the need to use different statistical
94 software not included in the packages, the use of unmixing models is generally restricted
95 to academics with a good knowledge of the procedure. Refinement of the sediment source
96 fingerprinting techniques requires open-source models that help the user in tracer
97 selection decisions and optimise this time-consuming process for non-expert and
98 academics with low programming and statistical skills by including the essential
99 statistical functions and plots.

100 To fill this gap, our objective was to develop for the first time an R package comprising
101 an unmixing model with the additional tools needed to comprehend the effect of the
102 selected properties on the model outcome. To this purpose, we create a new R package
103 that combines in a novel assemblage the tools needed to unmix sediment samples and the
104 previous statistical tests to select optimum tracers. Thus, we aim to provide an easy and
105 straightforward way to apply the sediment fingerprinting technique aimed at beginners or
106 non R users.

107 This paper presents the **FingerPro** package, a user-friendly application and freely
108 available software for users with limited or no expertise in statistics. Thus, any user could
109 implement the fingerprinting procedure with limited previous experience in the technique
110 and with no need for additional software for statistical analyses. Furthermore, unlike
111 previous models, this new tool to identify sediment provenance has been successfully
112 tested with artificial samples ([Gaspar et al. 2019b](#)).

113 The analyses explained in this research are based on 1) a reproducible data set example
114 of small catchment included in the package and 2) another example of ongoing research
115 in a medium-size catchment to further describe the capability of the package. The medium
116 size catchment is selected as representative of mountain headwaters (South Pyrenean
117 region) that supply water to reservoirs as siltation and pollution is one of the main
118 environmental issues worldwide ([Valero-Garcés et al. 1999](#)). Through these two
119 examples, the utility of the **FingerPro** package for applying tools aimed at pre-processing
120 input data or combining sources without significant differences before or after running
121 the unmixing model is shown. Through the provided examples, it is evident that
122 fingerprinting methods are necessary to identify sediment sources to establish
123 management strategies for ensuring water supply to the lowlands while preserving water
124 quality.

125 **2. METHODS**

126 Sediment fingerprinting requires a preliminary analysis to select a subset of
127 conservative tracers that discriminate the potential sources. Then, the relative contribution
128 of each source is estimated using a linear multivariate unmixing model. This procedure
129 is iterated considering the variability of the sediment sources to obtain the statistical
130 distribution of the source contribution.

131 *2.1 Statistical analysis for the selection of tracer properties*

132 Several statistical tests can be used to confirm source discrimination and select the
133 optimal subset of conservative tracer properties, such as the procedure suggested by
134 [Collins and Walling \(2002\)](#). However, the use of many tests could remove a considerable
135 number of tracers and therefore restrict the discrimination between sediment sources.
136 Consequently, none of the functions included in the **FingerPro** package are mandatory
137 and the tracer exclusions can be based on ‘expert judgement’ after visualising boxplots
138 and results from the statistical tests included. The tracer selection methods implemented
139 in the package are:

140 i) Range test: the minimum and maximum values of the tracer properties in the
141 sediment sources are compared to those of the mixtures. The tracers falling out of the
142 range of the selected sources are removed from subsequent analyses. These properties
143 may not be conservative or their exclusion supports the existence of an additional hidden
144 source.

145 ii) Kruskal-Wallis H test: this is a rank-based nonparametric test used to determine if
146 there are significant differences between the medians of selected groups or sources. This
147 procedure removes tracers that do not show significant differences between at least two
148 of the sediment sources.

149 iii) Discriminant Function Analysis identifies the optimum set of tracers that
150 maximises the discrimination between the sediment sources whilst minimising the
151 number of tracers. This function executes a stepwise forward variable selection for
152 classification using the Wilk's Lambda criterion. The function selects the tracers based on
153 how much they decrease Wilks' lambda. At each step, the function includes the variable
154 that minimises the overall Wilks' lambda.

155 2.2 *Mixing model*

156 The relative contribution of each potential sediment source is determined using a
157 standard linear multivariate mixing model:

$$159 \quad \sum_{j=1}^m a_{i,j} \cdot \omega_j = b_i$$

158 which satisfies:

$$160 \quad \sum_{j=1}^m \omega_j = 1$$

$$161 \quad 0 \leq \omega_j \leq 1$$

162 where b_i is the tracer property i ($i = 1$ to n) of the sediment mixture, $a_{i,j}$ represents the
163 tracer property i in the source type j ($j = 1$ to m), ω_j is the unknown relative contribution
164 of the source type j , m represents the number of potential sediment sources and n is the
165 number of tracer properties selected.

166 This system of equations is mathematically determined if the number of tracers is
167 greater than or equal to the number of potential sources minus one ($n \geq m - 1$). The
168 procedure tries to find the source proportions that conserve the mass balance for all tracers
169 from the complete exploration of the parameter space (Palaz3n et al. 2015). All possible
170 combinations of each source contribution (0-100%) are examined in small increments,
171 using Latin hypercube sampling (LHS) (McKay et al. 1979). The quality of each

172 candidate is measured using the following function or goodness of fit (GOF), based on
173 the sum of squares of the relative error:

$$174 \quad GOF = 1 - \frac{1}{n} \times \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{|b_i - \sum_{j=1}^m \omega_j a_{i,j}|}{\Delta_i} \right)$$

175 where Δ_i is the range of the tracer property i , used as a normalisation factor. The
176 combinations that reproduce the observed sediment mixture with the maximum GOF are
177 selected as the solution.

178 ***2.3 Variability analysis of the sources***

179 In small to large size catchments, the heterogeneity of sediment tracers, defined by
180 different land uses, geomorphic processes, soil types or human activity, is always present.
181 For this reason, fingerprinting studies should correctly characterise source variability by
182 collecting several samples from each source. Thus, evaluation of the variability in tracer
183 data used to characterise sediment sources is important to correctly interpret the source
184 apportionment results.

185 Variability analysis is assessed following classical frequentist inference utilising a
186 Monte-Carlo method (Helton, 1994). A succession of deterministic calculations is
187 executed, each with different input values sampled from their respective distributions, to
188 obtain probability distributions of the targeted outcomes.

189 The heterogeneity of each source is considered as a t-distribution for each property.
190 The fingerprinting analysis of each sediment mixture is repeated by randomly sampling
191 the source probability distributions. For the first iteration, the central value of the source
192 distributions is used as a reference result. The corresponding output values are gathered
193 to infer the probability distribution of the potential source contributions. Several samples
194 must be collected for characterising each source to compute the mean and the SD of the
195 analysed tracer properties.

196 3. THE FINGERPRO PACKAGE

197 Application of the functions in the package allows the user to i) characterise the
198 different tracer properties and select the relevant variables; ii) unmix the sediment
199 samples and quantify the different source apportionment; iii) assess the effect of the
200 source variability; and iv) visualise and export the results. Thus, **FingerPro** package
201 proposes a step by step procedure divided into three main sections to help users in their
202 decisions.

203 3.1 *The example dataset*

204 The package includes a soil dataset from a small Mediterranean catchment (4 km²) that
205 contains high-quality radionuclide and geochemistry data to test the operation of the
206 functions and help the user to understand the model (Fig.1). This study area was selected
207 due to its heterogeneous land uses/land covers which are likely to exhibit large differences
208 in sediment tracer contents. Furthermore, the study area is located in a well-studied
209 catchment where several studies of soil redistribution ¹³⁷Cs derived rates were pursued
210 (Quijano et al. 2016; Lizaga et al. 2018). Thus, soil redistribution rates were used to
211 evaluate **FingerPro** model as a suitable tool in the northern-central part of the Ebro basin.
212 The results obtained by Lizaga et al. (2018) found that net soil loss values were 4 times
213 higher in agricultural lands than in pine forest highlighting the importance of the
214 vegetation cover and land management to prevent erosion processes and subsequent land
215 degradation.

216 The study area dataset is composed of 21 source sediment samples from 4 different
217 sources and 2 mixture samples. The sources are divided into agricultural (AG), old pine
218 forest (PI), recent pine forest (PI1) and degraded soil named subsoil (SS) which occupy
219 9%, 32%, 58% and 1% of the catchment area, respectively. The agricultural land use is
220 mainly composed of winter cereal crops and the pine afforestation forest is predominantly

221 *Pinus halepensis* Mill. The average temperature ranges from 5 °C to 18 °C, and the mean
222 annual rainfall is about 520 mm (AEMET).

223 **3.2 Input data**

224 The input variables need to be stored as an R table object. The dataset must satisfy the
225 following requirements: i) the first column represents the sample *id*; ii) the second column
226 is the source classification, containing target samples in the last place.

227 **3.3 Characterising the sediment samples**

228 One of the advantages of the **FingerPro** package is that it allows the user to analyse
229 and visually compare different tracer properties, using the state of the art of R packages:

230 The *boxPlot()* function displays a boxplot of each tracer property to help the user in
231 the decision by visualising the different concentrations of each tracer versus the mixture
232 sample. A parameter (*columns*) with the number of tracer properties in the boxplots is
233 provided. The number of columns (*ncol*) refers to the number of plots per row in the
234 display (Fig.2). The *boxPlot()* function could be used for tracer selection by helping the
235 user to visualise and select the tracers based on the boxplots and its expert knowledge.
236 Thus, the user visualises in the example dataset that most of the $^{210}\text{Pb}_{\text{ex}}$ in the mixture
237 sample likely comes from PI and PII sources and that ^{40}K is almost out of range (Fig.2).
238 Furthermore, by repeating this function after implementing each test for tracer selection,
239 users can envisage how representative the remaining tracers are.

240 The *correlationPlot()* function displays a correlation matrix of each tracer, divided by
241 the different sources to help the user by testing the conservatism of tracers by visualising
242 the relationships between the different tracers and sediment mixtures following the
243 methodology proposed by [Pulley et al. \(2015\)](#). A parameter (*columns*) with the number
244 of tracer properties in the correlation matrix is provided, along with the possibility to
245 include the sediment mixture (*mixtures = T*) in the matrix or to exclude it (by default). In

246 addition, in the correlation plot, once the users have selected the optimum set of tracers,
247 it is possible to visualise if the mixture samples fit inside the source distributions. If a
248 mixture sample is outside the sources distribution, then no solution exists or the mixing
249 model assumptions are not met.

250 The *PCAPlot()* function performs a principal components analysis on the given data
251 matrix and displays a biplot of the results, divided by the different sources, to help the
252 user in the decision. A parameter (components) with the number of principal components
253 to display is included.

254 The *LDAPlot()* function performs a linear discriminant analysis and visualises the data in
255 the relevant dimensions. A parameter (P3D) allows the user to display a 3D LDA graph
256 (Fig.3). This set of functions allows the user to visualise the principal components plot
257 and the linear discriminant plot after the statistical selection procedure. Thus, the plots
258 help the user to visually identify whether the excluded variables increase or decrease the
259 discrimination capacity between sources. Furthermore, the *LDAPlot()* function was used
260 in the catchment example to visualise the number of sources that show good
261 discrimination with this set of tracers (Fig.3). The function shows a large overlap between
262 PI and PI1 that would suggest merging both sources. Thus, after grouping PI and PI1 the
263 discriminant plot shows better discrimination between the selected sources (Fig.3).

264 ***3.4 Statistical test for selecting the optimal set of tracers***

265 The selection of the optimal tracers is usually based on the two-step procedure
266 proposed by Collins and Walling (2002), which includes some previous statistical
267 procedures such as the “range test”, the KW and the DFA test. Thus, **FingerPro** has
268 included these functions to support user decisions. However, this procedure might remove
269 too many tracers or include some inadequate properties and could, therefore, restrict the
270 discrimination between sediment sources. Hence, the procedure is included as an

271 individual and informative function to only use the steps needed and to prevent a
272 reduction in the source discriminations. For this reason, the tracer selection procedure
273 cannot be only based on statistical tests but also on the expert knowledge of the
274 geomorphological and hydrological processes of the catchment (Blake et al. 2018). Thus,
275 the boxplot chart, LDA plots and correlation plot included in the **FingerPro** package were
276 implemented to help the users in the decision.

277 The *rangeTest()* function excludes the tracer properties of the mixture/s outside the
278 lowest and highest values in the sediment sources.

279 The *KWTest()* function excludes tracers from the original dataset which do not show a
280 significant difference between sources. This function performs a Kruskal-Wallis rank-
281 sum test using the *kruskal.test()* function from the R package **stats**. A parameter to select
282 the p-value (*pvalue*) is provided.

283 The *DFATest()* function executes a stepwise forward variable selection, using the
284 Wilk's Lambda criterion, which maximises the discrimination between the sources whilst
285 minimising the number of tracers. This function performs a stepwise forward variable
286 selection using the *greedy.wilks()* function from the R package **klaR**. A parameter to
287 select the niveau (*niveau*) for an approximate F-test decision is provided with a default
288 value of 0.1. This value could be reduced to be more restrictive in the tracer selection
289 procedure. However, by reducing the value below 0.05 the statistical test could remove
290 the majority of the tracers with the subsequent decrease in the discrimination of the
291 different sources.

292 These three tracer selection methods were applied in the example dataset. In Fig.2 the
293 tracers removed by each method can be seen and, based on the boxplot graph, to decide
294 if it is suitable to use all of them or if the selected tracers represent a good approximation
295 of the dataset. After the implementation of the range test function, we can see in the

296 boxplot graph that effectively Pb, Zn and Cr have been removed. However, there are other
297 tracers such as ^{40}K , Sr, Fe, and V that remain in the dataset though they should not be
298 considered as tracers inside the source range. Furthermore, by using the LDA and PCA
299 plots we can decide if the use of other tracer selection methods decreases the
300 discrimination or if by using them we could remove a tracer with specific information.
301 As shown in Fig.4, by removing ^{226}Ra and Mn from the dataset by using the DFA after
302 the KW test, the LDA plot shows similar results. In addition, the arrows of the removed
303 tracers in the PCA plot were parallel to those that remain in the dataset. Thus, in this
304 example, the plot information suggests that including or removing ^{226}Ra and Mn should
305 not produce important variations in the discrimination of sources or the model results as
306 is evident in Fig.4.

307 ***3.5 Sediment unmixing***

308 The *unmix()* function assesses the relative contribution of the selected sediment
309 sources for each mixture in the dataset. A parameter (*samples*) with the number of
310 samples of the LHS is provided. The number of iterations (*iter*) in the source variability
311 analysis is also configurable. However, if the number of iterations is set as 1, results are
312 produced in a single analysis considering the sources mean value.

313 The *plotResults()* function displays a plot with the density distribution of the model
314 solutions and a table with the mean value and the standard deviation of the model
315 solutions (Fig.4). Besides, users can display the results in violin plots instead of density
316 plots by adding the word *True* to the violin option.

317 After the tracer selection procedure, **FingerPro** results reveal that 18% of the mean
318 sediment supply comes from agricultural land use and 34% and 47% from bare soil and
319 pine forest, respectively. The small standard deviation of the three sources together with
320 the high GOF value shows a good fit of the model to efficiently discriminate the selected

321 sources (Fig.4). However, users should be cautious about using GOF as an assessment of
322 model reliability. Recent research has shown models with a high GOF can still deliver
323 inaccurate results (Palazón et al. 2015; Gaspar et al. 2019b), but also has shown that all
324 models with low GOF always deliver wrong results.

325 The results of the example dataset are supported by soil erosion rates estimated with
326 ^{137}Cs by Lizaga et al. (2018) in a Mediterranean catchment comprising the one studied
327 here. Thus, 18% of the sediment contribution is supplied from 9% of the area under
328 agricultural management and 47% of the contribution comes from pine forest that
329 occupies 90% of the study catchment. Relatively speaking, the subsoil was the main
330 source with 34% of the contribution for only 1% of the area taken by the bare soil in the
331 study catchment. Our results highlight the hazards that subsoils have on supplying
332 important amounts of sediments to the water systems.

333 ***3.6 Application in a Medium-Size catchment***

334 In this section, as an example, the results of applying the **FingerPro** package in a
335 medium-size catchment (Lizaga et al. 2019) are described. Its larger surface area and a
336 higher number of sources result in a more complex unmixing. For this reason, all the tools
337 added in the **FingerPro** package to help the users and characterise the unmixing dataset
338 are essential to reach robust results. Here, we highlight the most important decisions made
339 during the fingerprinting procedure and how the different tools included in the package
340 help the authors to unmix their data. To avoid repetition in this manuscript, only one
341 mixture sample collected at the outlet of the catchment is used to describe the FingerPro
342 utilities.

343 Following the application of the range test and Kruskal Wallis test, the final selection
344 was made based on expert judgment using the boxplots and correlation plots to finally
345 identify the conservative tracers. Fig.5 illustrates how some tracers pass the selection

346 tests, such as RT, KW and DFA, but show non-conservative behaviour, i.e. LF, Fe, Ti
347 and Ca. In addition, if we analyse the correlation plot of the tracers that shows non-
348 conservative behaviour, the sample mixture is located almost out of the point cloud. On
349 the other hand, the sample mixture is located inside the point cloud of the conservative
350 tracers. Thus, based on this information it was decided to select the tracers after passing
351 the KW test using expert knowledge, thus obtaining more defined results and higher GOF
352 (Fig.6). Hence, all the tools added in the **FingerPro** package to remove the tracers that
353 violate the principles of conservativeness are needed in fingerprinting studies. This
354 methodology suggests that including tracers with non-conservative or discordant
355 information into fingerprinting models does not add valuable information and could lead
356 the model to unpredictable results as it was found by [Lizaga et al. \(2020\)](#).

357 **4. CONCLUSIONS**

358 The application of mixing models it is necessary to understand source-tracer
359 relationships what is generally performed by applying different software's to select the
360 best combination of sediment tracers. With **FingerPro**, diverse test and mechanisms have
361 been incorporated for tracer selection in a single software. Furthermore, the inclusion of
362 several plot functions such as *boxPlot*, *correlationPlot*, *LDAPlot* and *PCAPlot* allows the
363 user to check if the selected tracers are suitable for the unmixing process. This package
364 for sediment source fingerprinting in hydrological systems offers a wider and easier
365 application in catchments affected by natural and human-induced changes.

366 Due to the increasing attention in tracing sediment methods and the need to select the
367 best tracer combination, an open-source tool that includes all the steps for sediment
368 unmixing is a key tool for the unmixing process. The example dataset included in
369 **FingerPro** provides evidence of the large sediment supply and severe soil loss caused by
370 land degradation and bare soil. In addition, the agreement between the unmixing results

371 obtained from the example dataset with the ^{137}Cs derived rates supports the capability of
372 the model for the sediment fingerprinting task. These results reflect the high importance
373 of creating a low time-consuming and open-source unmixing model that combines the
374 necessary tools to solve environmental issues such as reservoir siltation or soil loss and
375 trace the sediment provenance.

376 **FingerPro** provides the users with tools to i) characterise the different sediment
377 sources, establish correlations between the tracers and assist the selection of the optimal
378 tracers, ii) graph the results using the state of the art of R packages iii) unmix sediment
379 samples to estimate the apportionment of the sediment sources and iv) test the model
380 using data from a Mediterranean study catchment included in the package.

381 In addition, the example dataset and the explained results of a medium-size catchment
382 introduce the users on to the functioning and potential of the tools included in the
383 **FingerPro** package while also showing the advantages of the fingerprinting technique to
384 improve the understanding of sediment supply processes. Future research will concentrate
385 on keeping the **FingerPro** package updated with new and upcoming fingerprinting
386 techniques, such as the recently published Consensus Method ([Lizaga et al., 2020](#)) for
387 improving the selection of tracers, avoiding non-conservative and dissenting tracers.

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400 **Conflict of Interest:** The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

401 **Availability of data, material and Code availability:**

402 The R package source files are available via:

403 GitHub platform: <https://github.com/eead-csic-eesa/fingerPro>

404 Name of code: fingerPro

405 Name of the manual: fingerPro_manual 1.2.pdf

406 Developer and contact address:

407 Ivan Lizaga Villuendas (lizaga.ivan10@gmail.com) / Borja Latorre
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409 Year first available: 2018

410 Software required: R Program language: R

411 **Authors' contributions:** All authors contributed to the study conception and design. Ivan
412 Lizaga: Conceptualization, Writing - Original Draft, Software, Data Curation,
413 Methodology, Formal analysis, Investigation, Resources; Borja Latorre:
414 Conceptualization, Writing - review & editing, Software, Supervision, Methodology,
415 Formal analysis, Investigation, Resources; Leticia Gaspar: Conceptualization, Validation,
416 Data Curation, Investigation, Resources, Writing - review & editing; Ana Navas:
417 Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Writing - review & editing, Supervision,
418 Project administration, Funding acquisition.

419

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569

FIGURE CAPTIONS

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Fig.1 Location of the study area. 3D picture of the catchment created with a DEM and land cover map

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Fig.2 Boxplot of the tracer properties included in the data example of a small catchment. In different colours, the tracers removed by each statistical test

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Fig.3 LDA plot of the data example of a small catchment for the different land covers: agricultural (AG), old pine forest (PI); recent pine forest (PI) and subsoil (SS). a) Before running the statistical test, the dataset shows collinearity. b & c) 2D and 3D LDA display of the dataset after running the statistical selection. d) LDA display after merging both pines sources PI and PI1

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Fig.4 LDA, PCA and density plots of the unmixing process before and after the use of the DFA test for the different land covers: agricultural (AG), pine afforestation (PI) and subsoil (SS)

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Fig.5 Correlation plots of seven of the tracer properties of the medium size catchment example. Agricultural (AG), Forest (FO), subsoil (SS) and channel bank (CB)

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Fig.6 Scaled density plots and results of the unmixing process after the two different tracer selection approaches for the different land covers: Agricultural (AG), Forest (FO), subsoil (SS) and channel bank (CB)

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587

- Agricultural
- Pine forest
- Old pine forest
- Subsoil
- Mixture

0 250 meters

$42^{\circ} 25' N$
 $01^{\circ} 13' W$

Land_Use

- AG Agriculture
- PI1 Old afforestation
- PI New afforestation
- SS Subsoil
- mix Mixture sample

Range test

- KW test
- DFA test
- Selected tracers

LDA

LDA

Sources
 AG
 PI
 SS

PCA

PCA

42744

42744

42746

42746

Sources
 AG
 PI
 SS

id	GOF.mean	GOF.SD	AG.mean	AG.SD	PI.mean	PI.SD	SS.mean	SS.SD
42744	0.921	0.033	0.202	0.068	0.510	0.073	0.287	0.079
42746	0.926	0.035	0.304	0.061	0.471	0.076	0.225	0.067

id	GOF.mean	GOF.SD	AG.mean	AG.SD	PI.mean	PI.SD	SS.mean	SS.SD
42744	0.952	0.032	0.195	0.064	0.467	0.061	0.338	0.062
42746	0.953	0.037	0.295	0.075	0.458	0.083	0.247	0.077

GOF.mean	GOF.SD	FO.mean	FO.SD	AG.mean	AG.SD	SS.mean	SS.SD	CB.mean	CB.SD
0.713	0.016	0.002	0.008	0.403	0.128	0.280	0.080	0.315	0.153

GOF.mean	GOF.SD	FO.mean	FO.SD	AG.mean	AG.SD	SS.mean	SS.SD	CB.mean	CB.SD
0.933	0.017	0.003	0.009	0.362	0.084	0.285	0.035	0.351	0.073